

Semantic Encryption/Decryption: Utilizing Preprocessing of Data as a Security Mechanism in Machine Learning Models

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Figure 1: DALL-E rendering of OpenAI's detailed security schematics, 2024.

ABSTRACT

This paper introduces a novel conceptual framework, termed 'semantic encryption/decryption,' that introduces the use of preprocessing techniques in securing machine learning models. We explore this concept starting with the often employed training efficiency technique of normalization and then further investigate the lock-and-key concept of semantic encryption/decryption by utilizing a hashing mechanism on inputs. Our experimental validation demonstrates that this methodology not only secures models against unauthorized use but also maintains data integrity throughout the model's lifecycle. Specifically, the model achieved a MAPE of just below 6% when using correctly encrypted preprocessing conditions. Conversely, with incorrect encryption parameters, the error rate escalated dramatically, exceeding 1000%, highlighting

the potential of future preprocessing security measures. These findings illustrate how semantic encryption/decryption can mitigate unauthorized use and maintain data integrity, introducing a new paradigm in secure machine learning practices. This approach not only mitigates risks associated with data misuse but also extends the usability of machine learning models in sensitive and critical applications, creating a 'certificate of security' that is analogous to cryptographic systems where the model's utility is 'locked' unless the correct preprocessing 'key' is applied before inference.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Computing methodologies** → **Machine learning**; • **Security and privacy** → *Security services; Authentication; Access control.*

KEYWORDS

Machine Learning, Security, Data Preprocessing, Model Encryption, Semantic Encryption, Model Security, Normalization, Hashing, Image Processing

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1 BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

1.1 Introduction to Machine Learning Security

The proliferation of machine learning (ML) technologies in various sectors, particularly those involving sensitive data, underscores a critical need for robust security measures. As these technologies become integral to national and corporate security systems, the potential for model theft or misuse emerges as a significant threat. Unlike traditional IT data assets, ML models represent the semantics of the information they are trained on, so that, even if the internals of a model are secure, anyone with access to it could still gain information by examining the data it outputs.

1.2 Model Protection Challenges

- **Intellectual Property:** A model's utility and proprietary value can be exploited without the original developers' consent, leading to potential revenue and data security losses.
- **Operational Integrity:** Models that can be operated without preprocessing steps designed by their creators are at risk of misuse. By ensuring that a model only functions correctly with specific preprocessing, you create an operational dependency that acts as a form of security.
- **Cost of Model Theft:** The theft and misuse of a machine learning model is not merely a loss of data but a significant business risk, as the development of these models involves considerable investment. Protecting these assets is crucial for maintaining competitive advantage and operational security.

1.3 Addressing Unique Security Challenges

Machine learning models differ from other forms of digital assets because they encapsulate and reflect the characteristics of their training data. This makes them susceptible to inadvertent data leaks if not adequately secured, which is especially concerning in contexts where models handle classified or sensitive information. Traditional security measures that protect data at rest and in transit are insufficient for models in operation, which are vulnerable to extraction and reverse engineering. Encryption, model obfuscation, and input sanitization are recommended by the OWASP Foundation to prevent model theft by making it harder to access or reverse engineer the model [1].

1.4 Adding a Lock and Key to Privacy-Preserving Machine Learning

A significant body of research has been devoted to developing methods that ensure the privacy and security of data within ML applications. A number of these concepts and methods have been captured under the framework of 'Privacy-Preserving Machine Learning' (PPML)[3] with a focus on protecting and anonymizing data. While the concepts and methods captured under PPML address security and privacy of data within a model, a model's output can be just as revealing and valuable. Semantic encryption/decryption mitigates that potential vector by reducing the utility of model outputs

when used without the correct semantic encryption/decryption preprocessing scheme.

1.5 Need for Robust Security Mechanisms

In essence, PPML is the heavy-tint over the model's windows, while semantic encryption/decryption is the lock on the door. The novel approach of semantic encryption/decryption ensures that the model performs optimally only with correctly preprocessed inputs, creating a lock-and-key mechanism for model operation. Incorrect or unauthorized preprocessing results in degraded model performance, rendering the model useless without the proper 'key.'

1.6 Conclusion

Protecting machine learning systems involves more than safeguarding data; it requires securing the models themselves to ensure they are not misused. Our approach of semantic encryption/decryption offers a promising avenue for achieving this, ensuring that models deliver value only in their intended context and preventing their unauthorized exploitation.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Dataset Description: BodyM Dataset

The BodyM Dataset, provided by Amazon, is a comprehensive collection of body measurements and corresponding silhouettes from 2505 subjects [2]. Each subject in the dataset is represented with:

Figure 2: Sample of front-facing and side-facing of subject. BodyM Dataset.[2].

- **Silhouette Images:** Two black-and-white masked images per subject, one of the front of the subject and one of the profile of the subject.
- **Height and Weight:** Basic biometric indicators.
- **Gender:** Recorded for demographic analysis.
- **Body Measurements:** 14 detailed metrics including ankle, arm, bicep, calf, chest, forearm, hip, leg, shoulder, thigh, waist, and wrist girths, as well as arm-length and shoulder-to-crotch length.

Table 1: Sample of Height, Weight & Gender Data

Height (cm)	Weight (kg)	Gender
160.0	92.4	female
175.5	102.8	female
181.5	111.8	male

Table 2: Sample of Body Measurements Data

Arm-Length (cm)	Bicep (cm)	...
52.90237808227539	33.294395446777344	...
46.76323318481445	28.288970947265625	...
53.288597106933594	30.80095863342285	...

- **Data Split:** The dataset is divided into Training, Test Set A, and Test Set B. The subjects in all three datasets were scanned in a lab for body metrics. The photographs in Training and Test Set A were taken in a controlled environment while Test Set B were taken in varied conditions to simulate real-world variability.

This dataset is particularly valuable for studies like ours due to its robust, real-world applicable data, making it ideal for testing the effectiveness of preprocessing techniques in a controlled yet diverse setting. To aid in maintaining clarity, we opted to limit the output down to one of the 14 output metrics, choosing the 'bicep' as our single output measurement.

2.2 Experimental Design

2.2.1 Phase 1: Normalization.

- **Objective:** Demonstrate semantic encryption/decryption through normalization, a commonly understood ML preprocessing technique.
- **Procedure:** Normalization was applied to the height and weight metrics, customizing the scale based on the training data's statistical characteristics, thus embedding a unique 'key' for decryption.
- **Rationale:** This phase illustrates how a common technique can secure the model by hampering its functionality when using unscaled inputs.

Listing 1: Normalization of Height & Weight Data

```
hwg_metadata['height_cm'] = (hwg_metadata['height_cm'] -
    hwg_metadata['height_cm'].min()) /
    (hwg_metadata['height_cm'].max() -
    hwg_metadata['height_cm'].min())
hwg_metadata['weight_kg'] = (hwg_metadata['weight_kg'] -
    hwg_metadata['weight_kg'].min()) /
    (hwg_metadata['weight_kg'].max() -
    hwg_metadata['weight_kg'].min())
```

2.2.2 Phase 2: Hashing Inputs.

- **Objective:** Implement hashing to directly secure inputs by transforming them into a single encrypted format.

- **Procedure:** The values for height, weight and gender were concatenated into a single string and then subjected to a hashing process. This approach transformed the three metrics into one encrypted input for training and thus is the 'key' to unlock the utility of the model.
- **Rationale:** This method ensures that the model operates effectively only with inputs that match the hashed format generated during training, acting as a robust security layer against unauthorized access.

Listing 2: Concatenation and Hashing of Metrics into Single Feature.

```
combined_string = f"{height}{weight}{gender}"
hasher = hashlib.sha256(combined_string.encode())
hash_bytes = hasher.digest()
hash_int = int.from_bytes(hash_bytes, byteorder='big')
return hash_int % modulus
```

2.2.3 Phase 3: Image Manipulation.

- **Objective:** Utilize inherent data characteristics to introduce security with relatively simple preprocessing techniques, employing image inversion and pixel value clipping.
- **Procedure:** Preprocess images by clipping non-zero pixel values to 1 to create a binary mask, then invert these values to form the unique preprocessing 'key' required by the model.
- **Rationale:** This phase demonstrates how straightforward manipulations of image data can effectively act as a security measure, securing the model against misuse if not preprocessed correctly during inference.

Listing 3: Image Inversion

```
def process_image(image_path, size=(128, 128)):
    image = Image.open(image_path)
    image = ImageOps.grayscale(image)
    image = image.resize(size)
    image = np.asarray(image)
    # inversion
    image = (image > 0).astype(int)
    image = 1 - image
    return image
```

2.3 Model Architecture and Training

The model used was a convolutional neural network (CNN) designed to process both numerical data and image inputs effectively, focusing on the predictive task of determining bicep girth based on the processed inputs.

Listing 4: Input Layer of Normalized Model Architecture

```
input_front = tf.keras.layers.Input(shape=(128, 128, 1))
input_profile = tf.keras.layers.Input(shape=(128, 128, 1))
input_height = tf.keras.layers.Input(shape=(1,))
input_weight = tf.keras.layers.Input(shape=(1,))
input_gender = tf.keras.layers.Input(shape=(2,))
```

Figure 3: Simulated inversion of front-facing image of subject.

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Listing 5: Input Layer of Hashed Model Architecture.

```
input_front = tf.keras.layers.Input(shape=(128, 128, 1))
input_profile = tf.keras.layers.Input(shape=(128, 128, 1))
input_hash = tf.keras.layers.Input(shape=(1,))
```

2.4 Training and Evaluation

The training of the model was conducted with normalization of height and weight as the semantic encryption/decryption preprocessing method for Phase 1 and concatenating and hashing height, weight and gender into a single input for Phase 2. Evaluation was conducted by encoding the respective inputs with both correct and incorrect preprocessing parameters to assess their impact on the accuracy and utility of the model. This dual approach allowed us to directly compare performance outcomes and validate the effectiveness of each preprocessing technique in safeguarding the model.

2.5 Statistical Analysis

The performance of the model under the different preprocessing scenarios was analyzed by inputting the 1,160 samples in the Test Set B group of the BodyM dataset, with a focus on the resultant Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) of the entire Test Set B dataset to quantify the impact of preprocessing on model accuracy and security.

2.6 Results of Phase 1: Normalization as a Method of Semantic Encryption/Decryption

The outcomes of Phase 1 provided a foundational understanding of how normalization, typically used as an efficiency technique, can be a form of semantic encryption/decryption that impacts model security and performance.

¹This architecture is also used in Phase 3: Image Manipulation

- **Performance with Correct Preprocessing:** When the normalization process was accurately applied to height and weight data, the model demonstrated a single digit MAPE (5.37%). Correctly normalized data ensured that the model operated within its optimal parameters, closely aligning with theoretical predictions.
- **Performance with Incorrect Preprocessing:** In contrast, when normalization was not applied, the model's performance suffered significantly. The MAPE observed was significantly higher. This degradation in model performance highlights the protective impact of proper preprocessing: without the correct 'key' of normalization, the model's output becomes unreliable and highly erroneous.

These findings underscore the dual utility of normalization in both enhancing model performance and securing it against unauthorized use. By making the model's accurate operation contingent on specific normalization steps, we effectively lock the model's utility, mitigating its misuse while maintaining data integrity.

Table 3: Results of Processing Test Set B Samples Through Normalized Model

Correctly Normalized MAPE	Nonnormalized MAPE
5.37%	2191.44%

Table 4: Comparison of Actual Measurements to Predictions Between Normalized and Nonnormalized Input Data (cm)

Actual Bicep	Normalized Input	Unnormalized Input
24.57407569885254	27.24456787109375	641.249267578125
34.60301971435547	33.71982955932617	802.9513549804688
35.46172332763672	36.411956787109375	870.0195922851562

2.7 Results of Phase 2: Hashing Inputs as a Method of Semantic Encryption/Decryption

Following the implementation of Phase 2, the experiments demonstrated notable variations in model performance based on the precision of the preprocessing steps applied:

- **Performance with Correct Preprocessing:** When inputs were hashed correctly using the predefined modulus during the preprocessing, the model achieved a similar MAPE (5.99%) to the model from Phase 1 (5.37%).
- **Performance with Incorrect Preprocessing:** Conversely, when the hashing parameters were altered (incorrect modulus used), the model's performance significantly declined. The MAPE increased drastically, exceeding the baseline by large margins. This substantial increase in MAPE under incorrect preprocessing conditions illustrates the critical role of precise, data-dependent preprocessing in the security framework of semantic encryption/decryption.

These results affirm the potential of using hashing, a relatively straightforward cryptographic technique, to enhance the security of machine learning models. By tying the model’s functionality to specific, controlled preprocessing steps, hashing effectively protects the model from unauthorized access and misuse, further validating the broader concept of semantic encryption/decryption introduced in this research.

Table 5: Results of Processing Test Set B Samples Through Hashed Model

Correctly Hashed MAPE (<i>modulus</i> = 10000)	Incorrectly Hashed MAPE (<i>modulus</i> = 10000 ²)
5.99%	1002.51%

Table 6: Comparison of Actual Measurements to Predictions Between Correctly and Incorrectly Hashed Input Data (cm)

Actual Bicep	Correctly Hashed Input (<i>modulus</i> = 10000)	Incorrectly Hashed Input (<i>modulus</i> = 10000 ²)
24.57407569885254	26.405004501342773	55.420555114746094
34.60301971435547	32.986228942871094	405.0690002441406
35.46172332763672	34.272830963134766	408.0690002441406

2.8 Results of Phase 3: Image Manipulation as the Method of Semantic Encryption/Decryption

Following the implementation of Phase 3, the experiments showed a significant impact on model performance based on if the image was correctly inverted prior to inference.

- **Performance with Correct Preprocessing:** When images were preprocessed as designed, the model maintained high accuracy, with performance metrics similar (4.66%) to those of Phase 1 (5.37%) and 2 (5.99%).
- **Performance with Incorrect Preprocessing:** The model exhibited severe performance degradation when the image did not go through an inversion step, validating the effectiveness of semantic encryption through image preprocessing.

These results emphasize the potential of using simple image manipulation techniques to secure machine learning models, further validating the concept of semantic encryption/decryption introduced in this paper.

Table 7: Results of Processing Test Set B Samples Through Image Inversion Model

Inverted Image MAPE	Uninverted Image MAPE
4.66%	19366.91%

Table 8: Comparison of Actual Measurements to Predictions Between Inverted and Uninverted Images as Input Data (cm)

Actual Bicep	Inverted Image Input	Uninverted Image Input
24.57407569885254	24.165306091308594	5738.03369140625
29.43222427368164	28.968679428100586	5941.859375
26.16543960571289	27.879959106445312	6061.5166015625

2.9 Conclusion

This methodology section details a comprehensive approach to demonstrating the effectiveness of semantic encryption/decryption techniques in machine learning. The experiments utilize normalization, hashing, and image preprocessing to secure model utility. Through structured experimentation with the BodyM Dataset, we illustrate how these preprocessing techniques protect against unauthorized use through unique data-dependent preprocessing keys.

3 GUIDELINES FOR IMPLEMENTING SEMANTIC ENCRYPTION/DECRYPTION

This section introduces a set of principles designed to help practitioners effectively implement semantic encryption/decryption in their machine learning systems. These guidelines are derived from the experimental results and aim to provide a conceptual framework that balances security needs with model performance.

(1) **Data and Intent Dependency**

The method of securing a model through semantic encryption/decryption should be fundamentally dependent on the nature of the data and the intended use of the model. This ensures that the security measures are tailored to the specific characteristics and vulnerabilities of the data, as well as the functional requirements of the model.

(2) **Impact on Model Performance**

While the primary aim of semantic encryption/decryption is to secure the model, it should ideally have minimal impact on the model’s performance. However, the acceptable level of performance degradation is subjective and should be determined by the practitioner based on the specific security and performance needs of the model. In cases where security is paramount, more degradation might be acceptable if the model still performs within acceptable limits of its optimal capacity.

(3) **Selective Application in Multi-Model Systems**

In systems employing multiple models, semantic encryption/decryption can be applied selectively. Specifically, it should be implemented in models that have direct exposure to external inputs or are at the front line of data ingestion. For instance, in architectures like Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) or Mixture of Experts (MoE), where multiple models interact, only the models that handle externally exposed inputs—such as an orchestrator layer or a gatekeeper model—require these security measures. Internal models that operate behind these gatekeepers can be exempt, as long as they are shielded from direct external interaction.

These guidelines aim to establish a robust framework that aids in the strategic implementation of semantic encryption/decryption across different types of machine learning applications, ensuring that security measures are both effective and appropriately integrated according to the operational context and specific needs of the system.

4 CONCLUSION

This research has effectively demonstrated the efficacy of semantic encryption/decryption through preprocessing techniques in securing machine learning models. Our findings illustrate how normalization, typically seen as an efficiency technique, can also play a role in semantic encryption/decryption. Furthermore, we expanded the security framework to include hashing and image preprocessing, both of which reinforce the concept of a lock and key within Privacy-Preserving Machine Learning methodologies.

The study proposed an initial set of guidelines to aid in implementing these techniques depending on the specific needs of the data and the operational intent of the model. By embedding security features directly into the preprocessing steps, we have devised a

novel method that ensures models function as intended only under specific, controlled conditions. This approach adds another layer of protection to the data and semantics captured in a model or system of models.

Moving forward, we encourage further exploration into the scalability of these methods across different computing environments, their applicability to diverse types of machine learning models, and the integration of more advanced cryptographic techniques into preprocessing workflows. Expanding this research could lead to more robust solutions and standardizations to address the evolving challenges of machine learning security and foster broader adoption and trust in these protective technologies.

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